

Kinetics of surface-catalyzed autoxidation of aqueous sulfur dioxide in cobalt(III) oxide suspensions[†]

D. S. N. Prasad^a, R. K. Mehta^g, P. Parashar^b, P. V. S. Madnawat^c, A. Rani^d, U. Singh^e, S. V. Manoj^f,
S. P. Bansal^g and K. S. Gupta^{g*}

^aGovernment College, Jhalawar; ^bL.B.S. College, Jaipur; ^cGyanjyoti College, Srikanpur; ^dGovernment College, Kota; ^eGovernment College, Sawai Madhopur; ^fMaharshi Arvind College of Engineering, Jaipur; ^gDepartment of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, India

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The surface-catalyzed autoxidation of sulfur(IV) in acetate buffered suspensions of Co₂O₃ obeys the kinetic rate law (A),

$$-\frac{d[S(IV)]}{dt} = (k_3 + k_4 [H^+]^{-1}) [S(IV)] [Co_2O_3] \quad (A)$$

In unbuffered suspensions, the rate law (B), at constant pH, is obeyed,

$$-\frac{d[S(IV)]}{dt} = k_7 [Co_2O_3] [S(IV)] \quad (B)$$

The reaction is not inhibited by ethanol, and this rules out the operation of a radical mechanism. The suggested mechanism implicates the absorption of both O₂ and sulfur(IV) on Co₂O₃ particle surface. The electron transfer within the surficial complex is responsible for the oxidation of sulfur(IV).

Recently, the kinetics of autoxidation of aqueous sulfur dioxide in suspensions of several solid catalyst powders, such as manganese(IV) oxide¹, cobalt(II) oxide², copper(I) oxide³, atmospheric dust⁴, glass⁵, cadmium oxide⁶, silica⁷ and copper(II) oxide⁷ have been reported from this laboratory. As all these studies are important in understanding the mechanism of atmospheric acid precipitation in wetted aerosols, cloud and rain water, we report here the kinetics of the autoxidation of aqueous SO₂ catalyzed by Co₂O₃ particles in their suspensions. Previously, homogeneous cobalt(II) and cobalt(III) catalyzed autoxidation has been the subject of several studies⁸.

Results and discussion

Kinetics in buffered suspensions :

The log of solubility product of Co(OH)₃ at 19°, is reported⁹ to be -44.5, which is very low and with little possibility of its leaching in aqueous suspensions. Even then, the possibility of the catalytic activity of Co₂O₃ suspensions being due to leached trace cobalt ions was checked by determining the rate of autoxidation of sulfur(IV) in blank reaction, leachate solution and in suspension. Whereas in the first two the rate of autoxidation, R_{obs} was quite low, it was much higher in the latter (Fig. 1). The reaction in suspension thus appears to be surface-catalyzed.

Fig. 1. Disappearance of sulfur(IV) under different reaction conditions at $[S(IV)] = 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 4.88$ and $t = 30^\circ$: (Δ) $[Co_2O_3] = 0.2 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$, $[EDTA] = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (\bullet) $[Co_2O_3] = 0.2 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$, $[EDTA] = 1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (\otimes) with leachate of $0.5 \text{ g dm}^{-3} [Co_2O_3]$; (\blacktriangle) uncatalyzed reaction; (\circ) uncatalyzed reaction, $[EDTA] = 1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (\blacktriangledown) with leachate, $[EDTA] = 1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

A study of the effect of EDTA showed its $(1-2) \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ concentration to be quite effective in arresting the leachate and blank reactions completely but without any

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

effect on suspension catalyzed reaction as shown in Fig. 1. As, the leachate and blank reactions are trace metal ion catalyzed, these are seized by EDTA¹⁰.

An increase in [buffer] at a fixed pH, led to a decrease in the rate and hence in all kinetics experiments in buffered suspensions, [CH₃COONa] was fixed at 0.14 mol dm⁻³ and, wherever necessary, [CH₃COOH] was varied for varying pH. The results of variation in [Co₂O₃] and [S(IV)], were in agreement with the rate law (1),

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k_2 [\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3] [\text{S(IV)}] \quad (1)$$

From the linear plot of $R_{\text{obs}}/[\text{S(IV)}]$ vs $[\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3]$ (Fig. 2), the value of k_2 was found to be $1.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at pH 4.88 and 30°.

Fig. 2. Plot of $R_{\text{obs}}/[\text{S(IV)}]$ vs $[\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3]$ at pH 4.88 and 30°.

A variation in pH from 4.5 to 5.9 led to an increase in the rate of reaction, when the pH was increased. The results conformed rate law (2),

$$R_{\text{obs}} = (k_3 + k_4 [\text{H}^+]^{-1}) [\text{S(IV)}] [\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3] \quad (2)$$

From the linear plots of $R_{\text{obs}}/([\text{S(IV)}][\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3])$ vs $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ (Fig. 3), the values of k_3, k_4 pairs at different temperatures were determined to be $1.11 \times 10^{-3}, 1.61 \times 10^{-8}$ (30°); $1.01 \times 10^{-3}, 2.81 \times 10^{-8}$ (35°); $0.82 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}, 4.31 \times 10^{-8} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (40°). The overall empirical energy of activation was determined to be 70 kJ mol^{-1} .

Few kinetic runs were done in the absence of O₂ and in N₂ atmosphere. Under these conditions, oxidation of S(IV) was found not to occur. This not only rules out the possibility of the direct oxidation reaction between Co₂O₃ and S(IV) but also establishes oxygen as the reactant. The dependence of R_{obs} on O₂ could be studied in air-saturated (21% O₂) and O₂-saturated (100% O₂) suspensions only. The rate data under these conditions yielded an order of 0.55 ± 0.05 in

[O₂]. The complete rate law can, therefore, be written as

$$R_{\text{obs}} = (k_5 + k_6 [\text{H}^+]^{-1}) [\text{S(IV)}][\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3] [\text{O}_2]^{0.55} \quad (3)$$

where, $(k_3 + k_4 [\text{H}^+]^{-1}) = (k_5 + k_6 [\text{H}^+]^{-1}) [\text{O}_2]^{0.55}$

The sulfur(IV) autoxidation reactions which involve oxysulfur radicals are known to be strongly inhibited by ethaonol^{10,11}. Keeping this in view, the Co₂O₃ catalyzed reaction was studied in presence of ethanol (1×10^{-5} – 0.1 mol dm^{-3}). Surprisingly, ethanol did not inhibit the reaction.

Fig. 3. Plots of $R_{\text{obs}}/[\text{S(IV)}] [\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3]$ vs $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$.

Kinetics in unbuffered suspensions :

In unbuffered study, the desired initial pH was adjusted with HClO₄. On increasing pH (2–6), the rate of reaction decreased initially, reaching a minimum at about pH 4, and a further increase in pH resulted in a continuous increase in the rate (Fig. 4). An additional feature was the appearance of an initial rapid reaction above pH 4, the magnitude of which increased with the increase in pH. An exactly similar behavior was noted earlier^{2,5,7,18}. Kinetics were studied at pH 3.54 at which there was no initial rapid reaction and the results at this pH were in agreement with the rate law (4),

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k_7 [\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3] [\text{S(IV)}] \quad (4)$$

The value of k_7 was determined to be $1.51 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 30° and pH 3.54.

Fig. 4. Variation of R_{obs} with pH in unbuffered suspensions at $[\text{S(IV)}] = 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3] = 0.2 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$ and at $t = 30^\circ$.

Recent studies¹⁰ have shown that whereas the heterogeneous MgO^{14} , CdO^6 , SiO_2^7 , CdS^{10} and the homogeneous manganese(II)^{10,11}, iron(III)¹⁵ and silver(I)¹⁶ catalyzed autoxidation of sulfur(IV) proceed through a radical mechanism involving oxysulfur radicals, viz. SO_4^- , SO_3^- and SO_5^- , the heterogeneous CoO , MnO_2 and Ni_2O_3 catalyzed reactions involve non-radical mechanisms¹⁰. The radical reactions are strongly inhibited by organics particularly ethanol, methanol and benzene and, therefore, the effect of organics on reaction rate is used as a test for distinguishing radical and non-radical reactions¹⁰. Since Co_2O_3 catalyzed reaction is not inhibited by ethanol, the operation of radical mechanism is ruled out.

The surface catalyzed reactions in suspensions of solid powder catalysts are well known to involve the formation of surficial complexes by adsorption of both sulfur(IV) and O_2 on the particle surface as in case of catalysis^{1-7,10,12} by $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ ¹², Ni_2O_3 ¹³, CoO^2 , SiO_2^7 etc. Likewise, the kinetics of the Co_2O_3 catalyzed reaction may also be explained in a similar manner.

An unequivocal interpretation of observed increase in rate, when the pH is increased, is rendered difficult by following three possibilities of the origin of hydrogen ion concentration dependence. First, the rate increase on increasing pH could be due to the formation of more reactive SO_3^{2-} from HSO_3^- . When the pH is increased, the relative proportion of $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}]$ increases in consonance with the following equilibria⁸ which govern the concentration of dominant sulfur(IV) species in aqueous solutions,

Second, as with other metal oxides¹⁷, the hydroxylation of Co_2O_3 in aqueous suspension, as in eqns. (7–8), occurs¹⁷,

Although the value of pH of zero point charge, pH_{zpc} , of Co_2O_3 is not reported, going by the values for other metal oxides¹⁷, e.g. Fe_2O_3 , Cr_2O_3 , its value is expected to be around 7. So in the pH range of 4.5–5.9 used in buffered study, Co_2O_3 is expected to be present dominantly as $\square\text{-Co}(\text{OH}_2)^+$ and increase in pH should result in the conversion of $\square\text{-Co}(\text{OH}_2)^+$ into $\square\text{-Co}(\text{OH})$. If the latter be more reactive than the former, the observed pH-dependence can be explained. Third, a variation in pH entails a variation in buffer concentration and so the observed pH-dependence could be due to this reason as well.

In view of these possibilities it is difficult to know the real reason of pH-dependence. Ignoring pH-dependence, the results of the present study can be explained by the following mechanism, which is similar to those proposed in case of other catalysts^{2,7,18},

The proposed mechanism (9–12) leads to the following derived rate law (13),

$$\frac{-d[\text{S(IV)}]}{dt} = \frac{k_8 K_1 K_2 [\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3] [\text{S(IV)}] [\text{O}_2]}{1 + K_1 [\text{O}_2] + K_1 K_2 [\text{O}_2] [\text{S(IV)}]} \quad (13)$$

When the pH is fixed, the experimental rate law (3) reduces to eqn. (14),

$$\frac{-d[\text{S(IV)}]}{dt} = k_9 [\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3] [\text{S(IV)}] [\text{O}_2]^{0.55} \quad (14)$$

To be in conformity with the observed clear-cut first order dependence in $[\text{sulfur(IV)}]$, in the derived rate law (13) the inequality $(1 + K_1 [\text{O}_2]) \gg (K_1 K_2 [\text{O}_2] [\text{S(IV)}])$ must hold and hence the value of K_2 should be small. Under these conditions, the rate law (13) will reduce to eqn. (15),

$$\frac{-d[\text{S(IV)}]}{dt} = \frac{k_8 K_1 K_2 [\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3] [\text{S(IV)}] [\text{O}_2]}{1 + K_1 [\text{O}_2]} \quad (15)$$

which is in agreement, at least qualitatively, with the experimental rate law (14) as both rate laws require an order of less than 1 in $[O_2]$.

Two unusual features of kinetics in unbuffered suspensions are the appearance of initial rapid reaction above pH 4, and a minimum in rate around pH 4 when the pH is varied in the range 2–6. The phenomenon of initial rapid reaction has been noted earlier in the carbon catalyzed reaction by Brodzinsky *et al.*¹⁸ and in CoO^2 , silica⁷ and glass⁶ catalyzed reactions by us. It has been taken as an evidence for the step (9) and thus supports the mechanism (9–12).

In unbuffered suspension, the rate increase on decreasing pH below 4, could be either due to greater reactivity of $SO_2 \cdot H_2O$ or due to escape of SO_2 from acidic solution. The lower sulfate recovery in such solutions supports the latter possibility. Indeed, escape of SO_2 from low pH solutions has been noted earlier^{2,18}.

Experimental

Cobal(III) oxide, Co_2O_3 (Sisco-Chem), sodium sulfite (E. Merck) and other chemicals (A.R.) were used. The single point B.E.T. surface area of Co_2O_3 was $3.54 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. The experimental procedure was the same as described earlier^{1–7}. The reactions were conducted in thermostated Erlenmeyer flasks and the reaction mixture was stirred continuously at $1500 \pm 100 \text{ rpm}$ using a magnetic bar to allow the passage of atmospheric oxygen and to save the reactions from becoming oxygen mass transfer controlled. The reactions were initiated by adding Co_2O_3 to the sulfite. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating unreacted sulfur(IV) iodometrically using starch as indicator. Co_2O_3 was shown not to interfere in the estimation. The treatment of kinetics results obtained in this study is based on determination of initial rates, R_{obs} , which were reproducible to within $\pm 10\%$.

In acetate buffered suspensions (pH 4.5–5.9) chemical analysis of the final reaction solution showed sulfate to be the only oxidation product and sulfate recovery, as $BaSO_4$, was $98 \pm 1\%$ of the theoretical value in accordance with the stoichiometric eqn.,

However, in low pH unbuffered suspensions, in which initial pH was adjusted to 2.02 with dilute perchloric acid, while sulfate was again the only oxidation product, its recovery as $BaSO_4$ was low at $79 \pm 4\%$. It appears that some sulfur(IV) escapes as SO_2 from these solutions.

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